

- 1) Grammatical rules must be used in speech instantly after learning them
- 2) Learners should speak and listen to the speech as much as possible
- 3) Students have to think in a target language (English), not in a native language

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LEARNING THEORIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AND THEIR IMPORTANCE

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Annotation: The thesis discusses different theories of language acquisition which are important in teaching and learning English. As language acquisition refers to how humans can develop the ability to understand and use language,

numerous language acquisition theories in the English Language aim to understand and explain how the learning process starts and progresses.

Key words: language acquisition, learning theories, behaviorism, cognitivism, constructivism, humanism, connectivism.

Teaching and learning may appear to be a universal process. After all, everyone goes to school and learns more or less the same thing, right? Well, not quite. As the prolific number of educational theorists in learning claim, there's actually an impressive variety of educational approaches to the art and science of teaching. Many of them have been pioneered by educational theorists who've studied the science of learning to analyze what works best and for whom. "Learning is defined as a process that brings together personal and environmental experiences and influences for acquiring, enriching or modifying one's knowledge, skills, values, attitudes, behavior and worldviews," notes the International Bureau of Education. "Learning theories develop hypotheses that describe how this process takes place", they noted.

In general, there are five widely known learning theories which teachers rely on:

- **Behaviorism** learning theory
- **Cognitive** learning theory
- **Constructivism** learning theory
- **Humanism** learning theory
- **Connectivism** learning theory

Educational theorists, teachers, and experts claim these theories can inform successful approaches for teaching and serve as a basis for designing lesson plans and curriculum.

Theories in education didn't begin in earnest until the early 20th century, but curiosity about how humans learn dates back to the ancient Greek philosophers Socrates, Plato and Aristotle. They explored whether knowledge and truth could

be found within oneself (rationalism) or through external observation (empiricism). By the 19th century, psychologists began to answer this question with scientific studies. The goal was to understand objectively how people learn and then develop teaching approaches accordingly. In the 20th century, the debate among educational theorists centered on behaviorist theory versus cognitive psychology. Or, in other words, do people learn by responding to external stimuli or by using their brains to construct knowledge from external data?

The first theory is Behaviorism. As *Simply Psychology* puts it: "Behaviorism is only concerned with observable stimulus-response behaviors, as they can be studied in a systematic and observable manner." Learning is based on a system of routines that "drill" information into a student's memory bank, as well as positive feedback from teachers and an educational institution itself. If students do an excellent job, they receive positive reinforcement and are signaled out for recognition.

According to the theory of Cognitivism, learning relies on both external factors (like information or data) and the internal thought process. Developed in the 1950s, this theory moves away from behaviorism to focus on the mind's role in learning. According to the International Bureau of Education "In cognitive psychology, learning is understood as the acquisition of knowledge: the learner is an information-processor who absorbs information, undertakes cognitive operations on it and stocks it in memory."

Constructivism is defined that the learner builds upon his or her previous experience and understanding to "construct" a new understanding. The passive view of teaching views the learner as 'an empty vessel' to be filled with knowledge," explains *Simply Psychology*, "whereas constructivism states that learners construct meaning only through active engagement with the world (such as experiments or real-world problem solving)."

Humanistic theorists explain their approach as a "learner- centric". A "learner- centric approach" in which the potential is the focus rather than the method or

materials. With the understanding that people are inherently good, humanism focuses on creating an environment conducive to self-actualization. In doing so, learners' needs are met and they are then free to determine their own goals while the teacher assists in meeting those learning goals.

Connectivism. Informed by the digital age, connectivism departs from constructivism by identifying and remediating gaps in knowledge. Strongly influenced by technology, connectivism focuses on a learner's ability to frequently source and update accurate information. Knowing how and where to find the best information is as important as the information itself.

To conclude, it is important to be aware of learning theories for teachers as they conduct their lessons in the way can meet students' expectation. Not all students are the same in a class, it is obvious, they have different ability in learning language. No two students learn in the exact the same way or at the exact same rate. Teachers should be able to evaluate the dynamic of the lesson and take into consideration students' needs and wants. Although espousing a particular learning theory isn't necessarily required in most teaching roles, online learning author and consultant Tony Bates points out that most teachers tend to follow one or another theory, even if it's done unconsciously.

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